

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
FLOXETINE & OLANZAPINE BY USING RP- HPLC****D.Kishore Kumar Patnaik*, Santanu Kumar Hotta, Chaitanya Bangari,
Dr.M.B.Venkatapati Raju**

Avanathi Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162.

Article Received: March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine by using Agilent C18 column (4.6×150mm)5μ, flow rate was 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio was (60:40 v/v) methanol: Phosphate buffer pH 3.0, detection wavelength was 256 nm. The instrument used was WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 996, Empower-software version-2. The retention times were found to be 2.327 mins and 4.342 mins. The % purity of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine was found to be 99.84% and 100.14% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Fluoxetine and Olanzapine such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 2937, 1.3 and 2300 and 1.3, the resolution was found to be 4.6. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine was found in concentration range of 50μg-250μg and 10μg-50μg and correlation coefficient (r²) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery was found to be 100.07% and 100.06%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.3 and 0.39, % RSD for intermediate precision was 0.1 and 0.16 respectively. The precision study was precision, robustness and repeatability. LOD value was 3.041 and 3.08 and LOQ value was 9.79 and 10.37 respectively.

Keywords: Fluoxetine, Olanzapine, methanol and Phosphate buffer.**Corresponding author:****D.Kishore Kumar Patnaik,**

Avanathi Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162.

pharmamadhuphd@gmail.com, 7799263656.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Kishore Kumar Patnaik *et al*, *The Analytical Method Development And Validation For The Simultaneous Estimation Of Fluoxetine & Olanzapine By Using Rp- Hplc.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

The analysis of Fluoxetine & Olanzapine by simultaneous estimation by RP-HPLC. Spectrophotometer, HPLC and HPTLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the simultaneous estimation of Fluoxetine & Olanzapine in pharmaceutical dosage form[1].

Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous analysis of Fluoxetine & Olanzapine. The developed method will be validated conferring to ICH guidelines[2]

The Objective of the present work was to study the simultaneous estimation of Fluoxetine & Olanzapine by RP-HPLC method by optimizing the chromatographic conditions and to developed method is validated conferring to ICH guidelines for various parameters specified in ICH guidelines, Q2 (R1).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Analytical method development:****A. Selection of wavelength [3]**

A solution of 10 µg/ml of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine were prepared in milliQ water. The resulting solutions were scanned individually on HPLC PDA detector from 200 to 400 nm and also in UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The optimal response for three of them was obtained at 240 nm. Hence the complete method was processed at the wavelength of 240nm.

Preparation of standard solution : 10 mg of Fluoxetine and 10mg of Olanzapine were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and the volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give a concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution) Further 0.3 and 1.8 ml were pipetted out from the above stock

solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give a concentration of 30 µg/ml and 180µg/ml respectively[4].

Preparation of sample solution:

10 Tablets of contents were weighed and triturated in glass mortar. The quantity of powder equivalent to 10 mg of active ingredient present in Fluoxetine and Olanzapine was transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, 7 ml of diluent was added to it and was shaken by mechanical stirrer and sonicated for about 30 minutes by shaking at intervals of five minutes each and was diluted up to the mark with diluent to give a concentration of 1000 µg/ml and allowed to stand until the residue settles before taking an aliquot for further dilution (stock solution)⁵. 0.3 ml of upper clear solution was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted with diluent up to the mark to give the respective concentrations as per with standard solution. The solution was filtered through 0.45 µm filter before injecting into HPLC system.

Preparation of Placebo:

The amount of powdered inactive ingredient supposed to be present in 10 tablets were accurately weighed and transferred in to 10 ml volumetric flask, 7 ml of diluent was added and shaken by mechanical stirrer and sonicated for about 30 minutes by shaking at intervals of five minutes and was diluted up to the mark with diluent and allowed to stand until the residue settles before taking an aliquot for dilution. 0.1 ml of upper clear solution was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted with diluent up to the mark and the solution was filtered through 0.45 µm filter before injecting into HPLC system [6].

TRIALS**TRIAL 1:**

Method development for the drugs was initiated based on the individual chemical characteristics' and their methods given in individual journals [7-11].

	Trail -1	Trail 2	Trail 3	OPTIMIZED METHOD
--	----------	---------	---------	------------------

Mobile phase	Methanol: Phosphate buffer PH3 (70:30)	Methanol: Sodium acetate PH 4 (60:40)	Methanol: Ammonium acetate PH3 (70:30)	Methanol: Phosphate buffer PH3 (70:30)
Diluent	Methanol	Methanol	methanol.	Methanol
Flow rate	1ml/min	1.0ml per min	1.0 ml per min	1.0 ml per min
Column	Inertsil C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm)	Thermosil C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 µm)	Inertsil C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 µm)	Agilent C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 µm)
Detector wavelength	240 nm	240 nm	240 nm	240 nm
Column oven	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient
Injection volume	10µl	10µl	20µl	10µl
Running time	10 min	10 min	10 min	10 min
Fig	1	2	3	4

The amount of drug present was calculated by using the following formula:

For Flouxetine and Olanzapine:

$$\text{Assay\%} = \frac{\text{AT} \times \text{WS} \times \text{DT} \times \text{P} \times \text{Avg. Wt}}{\text{AS} \times \text{DS} \times \text{WT} \times 100 \times \text{Label Claim}} \times 100$$

Where:

AT = average area counts of sample preparation.

As= average area counts of standard preparation.

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg.

P = Percentage purity of working standard

LC = label claim of Flouxetine mg/ml.

The Standard, Sample and Blank Chromatograms for optimized method were shown in Fig: 5, 6&7

Method validation [12-28]:

The objective of validation of an analytical procedure is to demonstrate that it is suitable for its intended purpose. According to ICH guidelines, typical analytical performance characteristics that should be considered in the validation of the type of methods are:

SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

Sample solution of Flouxetine and Olanzapine were injected three times into HPLC system as per test procedure. The system suitability parameters were evaluated from standard Chromatograms obtained, by calculating the % RSD of retention times, tailing factor, theoretical plates and peak areas from three replicate injections.

Acceptance criteria:

1. The % RSD for the retention times of principal peak from 3 replicate injections of each Standard solution should be not more than 2.0 %
2. The number of theoretical plates (N) for the Flouxetine and Olanzapine peaks should be not less than 2000.

3. The Tailing factor (T) for the Flouxetine and Olanzapine peaks should be not more than 2.0.

From the system suitability studies it was observed that all the parameters were within limit. Hence it was concluded that the Instrument, Reagents and Column were suitable to perform the Assay.

The results were expressed in **Table: 2** and Chromatogram was shown in **Fig: 7**.

LINEARITY:

Preparation of sample stock solution:

About 50 mg of Flouxetine and 12 mg of Olanzapine samples was weighed in to 10ml volumetric flask, it was dissolved with diluent and the volume was made up to the mark with same diluent (5000µg/ml of Flouxetine and 1200µg/ml of Olanzapine).

Preparation of Level – I (50µg/ml of Flouxetine &10µg/ml of Olanzapine)

0.1ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level–II (100 µg/ml of Flouxetine &20 µg/ml of Olanzapine)

0.2ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level–III (150 µg/ml of Flouxetine & 30 µg/ml of Olanzapine)

0.3ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level–IV (200 µg/ml of Flouxetine & 40 µg/ml of Olanzapine)

0.4ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level–V (250 µg/ml of Flouxetine & 50 µg/ml of Olanzapine).

0.5ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

10µl of each level were injected into the system and recorded the peak response.

The chromatograms were recorded as show in **Figure 3.4 (a) – 3.4 (e)** and results are shown in **Table- 3 and 4**.

Procedure:

Each level solution was injected into the chromatographic system and the peak area was measured. A graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) was plotted and the correlation coefficient was calculated.

The linearity of the method was demonstrated over the concentration range of 10-100µg / ml. Aliquots of five levels were prepared from sample solution and labeled as solution 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively. The solutions were injected in to HPLC system as per test procedure. The Chromatograms were given in **Fig: 8,9,10,11 and 12**.

A calibration curve was plotted for concentration v/s peak area and was given in the **Fig: 13, 14&15**. The results were discussed in **Table: 4, 5& 6**.

Acceptance criteria

1. Correlation Coefficient should be not less than 0.9990.
2. % RSD of peak areas for Solution 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 should be not more than 2.0 %.

PRECISION:**Preparation of stock solution:**

50 mg of Flouxetine and 12mg of Olanzapine were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely. The volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution). Further 0.3 ml and 1.8 ml was pipette out from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 150 µg/ml and 30 µg/ml respectively.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and the areas for all five injections were measured in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

The Chromatograms were presented as **Fig: 16**.

The results were given in **Table: 7**.

Acceptance criteria:

1. % Relative standard deviation of peak areas and R_t should not be more than 2.0 %.

Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method. Precision was performed on different day by using different make column of same dimensions.

Preparation of stock solution:

50 mg of Flouxetine and 12mg of Olanzapine accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and the volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution) Further 0.3ml and 1.8ml were pipette out from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 150µg/ml and 30 µg/ml respectively.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and the area was measured for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area and R_t of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Two analysts as per test method conducted the study. For Analyst-1 the results are under precision (Repeatability) results and the results for Analyst-2 were discussed in **Table: 9**. Chromatograms were shown in **Fig: 17,18,19,20&21**.

Acceptance criteria:

1. % Relative standard deviation of peak areas and R_t should not be more than 2.0 %

ACCURACY:

Assay was performed in triplicate for various concentrations of Flouxetine and Olanzapine equivalent to 50, 100, and 150 % of the standard amount was injected into the HPLC system as per the test procedure.

Preparation of Standard stock solution:

50 mg of Flouxetine and 12mg of Olanzapine accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean

dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution)

Preparation Sample solutions:

Preparation of 50% solution (25 µg/ml of Flouxetine and 6µg/ml of Olanzapine):

From the above stock solutions take 2.5 ml and 0.6 ml into 10 ml dry volumetric flask, make up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 100% solution (50 µg/ml of Flouxetine and 12 µg/ml of Olanzapine):

From the above stock solutions take 5.0 ml and 1.2 ml into 10 ml dry volumetric flask, make up to the mark with diluent

Preparation of 150% solution (75 µg/ml of Flouxetine and 18 µg/ml of Olanzapine):

From the above stock solutions take 7.5 ml and 1.8 ml into 10 ml dry volumetric flask, make up to the mark with diluent.

These solutions were filtered through 0.45µm membrane and then each concentration; three replicate injections were made under the optimized conditions

Procedure:

The standard solution, Accuracy -50%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -150% solutions were injected. The amount found and amount added for Flouxetine and Olanzapine individual recovery and mean recovery values were calculated and the results were summarized in **Table:10,11&12**. The chromatograms were represented in **Fig: 22,23,24 and 25**.

Acceptance criteria:

The mean % recovery of the Flouxetine and Olanzapine each spike level should be not less than 98.0 % and not more than 102.0 %.

SPECIFICITY:

A) Flouxetine and Olanzapine identification:

Solutions of Standard and Sample were prepared as per test procedure and injected into the HPLC system. The recorded Chromatograms were shown in **Fig: 26 and 27**.

Acceptance criteria

Chromatogram of standard and sample should be identical with near Retention time.

B) Placebo interference:

A study to establish the interference of placebo was conducted. A sample of placebo was injected into the HPLC system as per the test procedure. The Chromatogram of placebo was represented as **Fig:28**

Acceptance criteria

Chromatogram of placebo should not show any peak at the retention time of analyte peak. There is no interference due to placebo at the retention time of analyte. Hence the method is specific.

C) Blank interference:

A study to establish the interference of blank was conducted. Diluent was injected into HPLC system as per the test procedure. The Chromatogram of blank was shown in **Fig: 28**.

Acceptance criteria

Chromatogram of blank should not show any peak at the retention time of analyte peak. There is no interference due to blank at the retention time of analyte. Hence the method is specific.

Ruggedness:

The simultaneous estimation of Flouxetine and Olanzapine was performed by different analysts on different days. The Chromatogram for Day-1, Analyst-1 was presented in **Fig: 30** and the results for were illustrated in **Table: 13**. The Chromatogram for Day-2, Analyst-2 was given in **Fig: 31** and the results were discussed in **Table: 14**.

Acceptance criteria

1. % Relative standard deviation of peak areas and R_t should not be more than 2.0 %.

Robustness:

The robustness of the proposed method was determined by analysis of aliquots from homogenous lots by differing physical parameters like flow rate and mobile phase composition, temperature variations which may differ but the responses were still within the specified limits of the assay.

a) Effect of variation of flow rate:

A study was conducted to determine the effect of variation in flow rate. The flow rate was varied at 1.0 ml/min to 1.4 ml/min. Standard solution 30 ppm Flouxetine and 180 ppm Olanzapine were prepared and analysed using the varied flow rates along with method flow rate.

The results are summarized. On evaluation of the above results, it can be concluded that the variation in flow rate affected the method significantly. Hence it indicates that the method is robust even by change in the flow rate $\pm 10\%$. The method is robust only in less flow condition. The effect of variation of flow rate was evaluated. The Chromatograms were shown in **Fig: 32 and 33**. The results were discussed in the **Table: 15, 16 and 17**.

Acceptance criteria

1. The tailing factor for Flouxetine and Olanzapine should be not more than 2.0 for Variation in flow.
2. The % RSD of Asymmetry and retention time for Flouxetine and Olanzapine should be not more than 2.0 % for variation in flow.

b) Effect of variation of mobile phase composition:

A study was conducted to determine the effect of variation in mobile phase ratio by changing the ratio of mobile phase. The Organic composition in the Mobile phase was varied from 30 % to 70 %.

Standard solution 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Flouxetine and 180 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Olanzapine were prepared and analysed using the varied mobile phase composition along with the actual mobile phase composition in the method. Standard solution was prepared and injected into the HPLC system and the Chromatograms which were recorded and shown in **Fig: 34 and 35**. The retention time values were measured and are given in **Table: 18, 19 and 20**.

Acceptance criteria

1. Tailing Factor of Flouxetine and Olanzapine drugs should not be more than 2.0 for Variation in composition of mobile phase.
2. The % RSD of tailing factor and retention times of Flouxetine and Olanzapine drugs should be not more than 2.0 for Variation in composition of mobile phase.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

For FLOUXETINE:

Preparation of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution:

10mg of Flouxetine was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. (Stock solution).

Further 0.1ml of the above stock solution was pipetted out into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Preparation of 0.15% solution at Specification level (0.004 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution):

Further 1ml of the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

0.1 ml of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution was pipette into a 10 ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 0.004 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

For Olanzapine

Preparation of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution:

10mg of Olanzapine working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and the volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. (Stock solution)

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Preparation of 0.22% solution At Specification level (0.006 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution):

Further 1ml of the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

0.22 ml of 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution was pipette into a 10 ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 0.006 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

LOD sample:

From the 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Flouxetine and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Olanzapine of the individual stock solution we prepared 0.004 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.006 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ injected into the system. The LOD is determined by the formula

$$\text{LOD} = \text{S/N}$$

Where

N = Average Baseline Noise obtained from Blank

S = Signal Obtained from LOD solution (0.25% of target assay concentration).

Chromatograms are represented in **Fig.no:36**

Acceptance Criteria: S/N Ratio value shall be not more than 3 for LOD solution.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ)

For Flouxetine:

Preparation of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution:

10 mg of Flouxetine was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. (Stock solution).

Further 0.1ml of the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents to give the concentration of 10 µg/ml.

Preparation of 0.05% solution At Specification level (0.015 µg/ml solution):

Further 1ml of the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 1 µg/ml.

0.05 ml of 10 µg/ml solution was pipetted into a 10 ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 0.015 µg/ml.

For Olanzapine:

Preparation of 10 µg/ml solution:

10mg of Olanzapine was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, about 7 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent to give the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. (Stock solution).

Further 0.1ml of the above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 10 µg/ml.

Preparation of 0.06% solution At Specification level (0.02 µg/ml solution):

Further 1ml of the above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 10 µg/ml.

0.06 ml of 10 µg/ml solution was pipetted into a 10 ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to give the concentration of 0.02 µg/ml.

LOQ SAMPLE:

From the 10 µg/ml of Fluoxetine and 10 µg/ml of Olanzapine of the individual stock solution we prepared 0.015 µg/ml and 0.1 µg/ml injected into the system.

LOQ is determined by the following formula:

$$LOQ = S/N$$

where

N = Average Baseline Noise obtained from Blank.

S = Signal Obtained from LOQ solution (1% of target assay concentration).

Acceptance Criteria: S/N Ratio value shall be 10 for LOQ solution.

Chromatograms are represented in **Fig. No: 37**.

RESULTS:

Fig 1 Chromatogram Of Trial 1

Fig 2: Chromatogram Of Trial 2

Fig 3: Chromatogram Of Trial 3

Fig 4: Chromatogram Of Trial 4:

Fig 5: Standard Chromatogram for Optimised Method

Fig 6: Chromatogram of Blank

Fig 7: Chromatogram for Placebo

**METHOD VALIDATION:
1. SYSTEM SUITABILITY**

Fig 8: Chromatograms for Assay sample

Fig 9: Chromatograms for Assay standard

2. LINEARITY

Fig:10 Chromatogram for Linearity level 1

Fig:11 Chromatogram for Linearity level 2

Fig:12 Chromatogram for Linearity level 3

Fig: 13. Chromatogram for Linearity level 4

Fig: 14 Chromatogram for Linearity level 5

Table:2 Linearity results for Flouxetine

S. No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	50 ppm	892464
2	II	100 ppm	1904884
3	III	150 ppm	2906620
4	IV	200 ppm	3800672
5	V	250 ppm	4738193
Correlation Coefficient			0.99932

Fig: 15 Calibration curve of Flouxetine

Table:3 Linearity results for Olanzapine

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	10 ppm	907953
2	II	20 ppm	1730043
3	III	30 ppm	2553693
4	IV	40 ppm	3283876
5	V	50 ppm	4144232
Correlation Coefficient			0.99916

Fig: 16 Calibration curve of Flouxetine

Parameter	Results for Flouxetine	Results for Olanzapine
Slope	19718	14311
Intercept	65498	49120
Correlation coefficient	0.9993	0.99916

Calibration parameters for Flouxetine and Olanzapine

PRECISION

A. Repeatability:

Fig: 17 Sample Chromatograms for Repeatability

Table: 8 and 9 Sample Chromatogram values for Repeatability

	Peak name	RT	Area
1	Flouxetine	2.321	2235319
2	Flouxetine	2.317	2240678
3	Flouxetine	2.323	2249490
4	Flouxetine	2.322	2245822
5	Flouxetine	2.324	2251694
Mean			2244601
Std.dev			6656.8
%RSD			0.3

	Peak name	RT	Area
1	Olanzapine	4.304	1501417
2	Olanzapine	4.300	1486940
3	Olanzapine	4.308	1490656
4	Olanzapine	4.310	1487329
5	Olanzapine	4.314	1490384
Mean			1491345
Std.dev			5881.4
%RSD			0.39

Acceptance Criteria:

The % RSD for the area and R_t of five standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

RUGGEDNESS

B)Intermediate precision (Analyst to Analyst variability):

Fig 20 Chromatograms for Intermediate precision

Table 5 and 6: Sample Chromatogram values for intermediate Precision

	Peak name	RT	Area
1	Flouxetine	2.328	2194758
2	Flouxetine	2.326	2195700
3	Flouxetine	2.327	2196191
4	Flouxetine	2.327	2195326
5	Flouxetine	2.331	2200951
Mean			2196585
Std.dev			2496.0
%RSD			0.1

	Peak name	RT	Area
1	Olanzapine	4.335	1456296
2	Olanzapine	4.336	1457422
3	Olanzapine	4.334	1456513
4	Olanzapine	4.337	1454579
5	Olanzapine	4.340	1451483
Mean			1455259
Std.dev			2347.6
%RSD			0.16

Acceptance Criteria: The % RSD for the areas and Rt's of five standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

ACCURACY**Fig 22 Standard Chromatogram for Accuracy****Fig 24 Chromatograms For Acc 100%**

Fig30:ChromatogramsForAcc150%

Table 12 Chromatogram Values For Accuracy of Fluoxetine

Sample No.	Spike Level	Amount (µg/ml) added	Amount (µg/ml) found	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50 %	5	4.9	98%	100%
		5	5.1	102%	
		5	5	100%	
2	100 %	10	9.88	98.8%	99.31%
		10	9.91	99.1%	
		10	9.95	99.5%	
3	150 %	15	14.89	99.2%	99.89%
		15	14.86	99.0%	
		15	14.99	99.79%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%

Table 12: Chromatogram Values For Accuracy of Olanzapine

	Spike Level	Amount (µg/ml) added	Amount (µg/ml) found	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50 %	5	4.9	98%	100%
		5	5.1	102%	
		5	5	100%	
2	100 %	10	9.88	98.8%	99.13%
		10	9.91	99.1%	
		10	9.95	99.5%	
3	150 %	15	14.89	99.2%	99.69%
		15	14.86	99.0%	
		15	14.82	99.79%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%.

ROBUSTNESS:**a) Effect of variation in flow rate:**

	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Platecount	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Fluoxetine	2.577	2715123	232327	2231.8	1.3	
2	Olanzapine	4.848	2508645	148154	2953.6	1.3	5.2

Name	Rt	Area	USP Platecount	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
Flouxetine	2.113	2511737	2063.0	1.3	
Olanzapine	3.935	2307025	2686.5	1.3	4.4

Table 16: Robustness results for Flouxetine (flow rate): Table 17: Robustness results for Olanzapine (flow rate):

S.No	Flow	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP
1	0.8	2953	1.3
2	1.0	2866	1.3
3	1.2	2686	1.3

S.No	Flow	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	2231	1.3
2	1.0	2114	1.3
3	1.2	2063	1.3

Results for actual flow (0.3ml/min) have been considered from Assay standard.

b) Effect of variation in mobile phase composition:

Fig 40: Chromatograms for more organic mobile phase

Table no:19Roubstness for Flouxetine

	Name	Rt	Area	USP Platecount	USP Resolution	USP Tailing
1	Flouxetine	2.113	2736327	2327.0		1.4
2	Olanzapine	3.395	2523661	2282.5	3.7	1.4

Fig:41Chromatogram for Less Organic Mobile Phase

Table no:20Roubstness for Olanzapine

	Name	Rt	Area	USP Platecount	USP Resolution	USP Tailing
1	Flouxetine	2.567	2748795	2867.5		1.2
2	Olanzapine	4.836	2577639	2312.2	5.3	1.2

	RT	AREA	HEIGHT
1	2.241	1208	135
2	3.790	1558	136

S.No	Changein Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	10% Less	2867	1.2
2	Actual	2860	1.3
3	10% More	2327	1.4

S.No	Changein Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	10% Less	2312	1.2
2	Actual	2860	1.2
3	10% More	2282	1.4

* Results for actual Mobile phase composition (65:35Methanol: Buffer) have been considered from Accuracy standard

LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD)

Fig:42 Chromatogram forFlouxetine and Olanzapine

Calculation of S/N Ratio for Flouxetine:

Average Baseline Noise obtained from Blank

: 48 μ V

Signal Obtained from LOD solution (0.15% of target assay concentration) : 146 μ V

S/N = 146/48 = 3.041

Acceptance Criteria:

S/N Ratio value shall be not more than 3 for LOD solution.

Calculation of S/N Ratio forOlanzapine:

Average Baseline Noise obtained from Blank

: 48 μ V

Signal Obtained from LOD solution (0.22% of target assay concentration) : 148 μ V

S/N = 148/48 = 3.08

Acceptance Criteria:

S/N Ratio value shall be not more than 3 for LOD solution.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ)

Fig: 43 Chromatogram For Flouxetine and Olanzapine

	RT	AREA	HEIGHT
1	2.771	4088	457
2	4.044	5258	459

Calculation of S/N Ratio forFlouxetine:

Average Baseline Noise obtained from Blank : 48 μ V

Signal Obtained from LOQ solution (0.05% of target assay concentration) : 470 μ V

S/N = 470/48= 9.79

Acceptance Criteria:

S/N Ratio value shall be not more than 10 for LOQ solution.

Calculation of S/N Ratio forOlanzapine:

Average Baseline Noise obtained from Blank : 48 μ V

Signal Obtained from LOQ solution (0.06% of target assay concentration) : 498 μ V

S/N = 498/48 = 10.37

Acceptance Criteria:

S/N Ratio value shall be not more than 10 for LOQ solution.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Flouxetine and Olanzapine by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Flouxetine and Olanzapine by using Agilent C18 column (4.6 \times 150mm)5 μ , flow rate was 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio was (60:40 v/v) methanol: Phosphate buffer pH 3.0, detection wavelength was 256 nm. The instrument used was WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 996, Empower-software version-2. The retention times were found to be 2.327 mins and 4.342 mins. The % purity of Flouxetine and Olanzapine was found to be 99.84% and 100.14% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Flouxetine and Olanzapine such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 2937, 1.3 and 2300 and 1.3, the resolution was found to be 4.6. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study of Flouxetine and Olanzapine was found in concentration range of 50 μ g-250 μ g and 10 μ g-50 μ g and correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery was found to be 100.07% and 100.06%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.3 and 0.39, % RSD for intermediate precision was 0.1 and 0.16 respectively. The precision study was

precision, robustness and repeatabily.LOD value was 3.041 and 3.08 and LOQ value was 9.79 and 10.37 respectively.

Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Flouxetine and Olanzapine in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Yuri Kazakevich and Rosario Lobrutto, HPLC for Pharmaceutical Scientists, 1stedition, Wiley Interscience A JohnWiley & Sons, Inc., Publication, (2007), PP 15-23.
2. A.BraithWait and F.J.Smith, Chromatographic Methods, 5thedition, Kluwer Academic Publisher, (1996), PP 1-2.
3. Dr. Kealey and P.J Haines, Analytical Chemistry, 1stedition, Bios Publisher, (2002), PP 1-7Chromatography, (online). URL:<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chromatography>.
4. Meyer V.R. Practical High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, 4th Ed. England, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, (2004), PP 7-8.
5. Andrea Weston and Phyllisr. Brown, HPLC Principle and Practice, 1st edition,Academic press, (1997), PP 24-37.

6. Sahajwalla CG a new drug development, vol 141, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, (2004), PP 421–426.
7. Draft ICH Guidelines on Validation of Analytical Procedures Definitions and terminology. Federal Register, vol 60. IFPMA, Switzerland, (1995), PP 1126.
8. Code Q2B, Validation of Analytical Procedures; Methodology. ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guidelines, Geneva, Switzerland, (1996), PP 1- 8.
9. Snyder LR practical HPLC method development, 2nd edition. John Wiley and sons, New York, (1997), PP 180-182.
10. V.Pranitha*, R.Saraswathi, Uma Maheshwar Rao V, Ajitha A, Rp-Hplc Method Development And Validation For Simultaneous Estimation Of Olanzapine And Fluoxetine In Tablet Dosage Form. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research & Analysis, Vol 4 / Issue 4 / 2014 /281-284.
11. [K. Basavaiah](#),¹ [N. Rajendraprasad](#),² and K. B. Vinay, socratic High-Performance Liquid Chromatographic Assay of Olanzapine: Method Development and Validation. SRN Analytical Chemistry, Volume 2014 (2014), Article ID 616941, 6 pages
12. V. Navya Sree, Chiranjeevi. G , Rajashekhar Prahalad , Srinivasa Reddy Edara, Method Development And Validation For The Simultaneous Estimation Of Fluoxetine Hydrochloride And Olanzapine In A Pharmaceutical Formulation By Rp-Hplc Method. International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Nano Sciences. 2(4), 2013, 514 - 529.
13. Gowthami Narapa Reddy, Karuna Priya Chitra, Method Development And Validation For The Simultaneous Estimation Of Olanzapine And Fluoxetine In Tablet Dosage Form By Rp-Hplc. An International Journal of Advances in Pharmaceutical Sciences, Volume 3 |Issue 3-4|May-August 2012|Pages 217-222.
14. Rubesh kumar S1*, P Gayathri3 , Duganath N1 , Kiran CH1 , Sridhar C2 , Jayaveera K N, Simultaneous Estimation of Fluoxetine HCl and Olanzapine in Bulk Drug and Pharmaceutical Formulation by Using UV-Visible Spectroscopy Method. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research 2011; 3(1): 52-55.
15. [Sejal Patel](#) and N. J. Patel, Simultaneous RP-HPLC and HPTLC Estimation of Fluoxetine Hydrochloride and Olanzapine in Tablet Dosage Forms. Indian J Pharm Sci. 2009 Jul-Aug; 71(4): 477–480.
16. Ashvin Dudhrejiya1*, Karishma Gandhi2 , Meera Maru3 , Navin Sheth, Development And Validation Of Stability Indicating Rp-Hplc Method For Simultaneous Estimation Of Sildenafil Citrate And Fluoxetine In Bulk & Tablet Dosage Form. International Bulletin of Drug Research., 4(6): 92-105, 2014.
17. [A Pathak](#), [Sadhana J. Rajput](#), Development of a stability-indicating HPLC method for simultaneous determination of olanzapine and fluoxetine in combined dosage forms. Reaserch gate.